

Comparison of Play Skills of Mothers of Children with Different Developmental Characteristics

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Abstract

This study aims to compare the play behaviors of mothers with children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), Down Syndrome (DS), and typically developing children. A total of 30 mothers with children between 36-48 months of age, who were educated in rehabilitation centers and preschool education institutions, participated in the study. Ten of these mothers had typically developing children, 10 had children with Down Syndrome, and 10 had children diagnosed with ASD. In the study, the play behaviors of the mothers with their children in a structured environment and with toys determined by the researcher were video recorded. The Control List for Supporting Play Skills Programme (OBEDEP-CL) was used to evaluate the mothers' play skills. According to the study's findings, no significant difference was found between demographic variables such as age, educational status, employment status, and number of children and play behaviors of the mothers. However, a statistically significant difference was found between the play skills of the mothers depending on the developmental disability group of the children. The study results reveal diversity in mother-child interactions of children with different developmental characteristics. These findings may provide awareness for special education specialists and parents to respond more effectively to the unique needs of children.

Keywords: Autism Spectrum Disorder, Down Syndrome, Typical Development, Parent, Play Behaviour

Öz

Bu araştırma, Otizm Spektrum Bozukluğu (OSB), Down Sendromu (DS) ve tipik gelişim gösteren çocuklara sahip annelerin oyun davranışlarını karşılaştırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Çalışmaya, rehabilitasyon merkezlerinde ve okul öncesi eğitim kurumlarında eğitim gören, gelişimsel olarak 36-48 ay aralığında olan çocuklara sahip toplam 30 anne katılmıştır. Bu annelerden 10'u tipik gelişim gösteren çocuğa, 10'u Down Sendromlu çocuğa ve 10'u OSB tanılı çocuğa sahiptir. Araştırmada, annelerin çocuklarıyla yapılandırılmış bir ortamda ve araştırmacı tarafından belirlenen oyuncaklarla gerçekleştirdikleri oyun davranışları video kaydına alınmıştır. Annelerin oyun becerilerini değerlendirmek için ise Oyun Oynama Becerilerini Destekleme Programı Kontrol Listesi (OBEDEP-KL) kullanılmıştır. Araştırma bulgularına göre, annelerin yaşı, eğitim durumu, çalışma durumu ve çocuk sayısı gibi demografik değişkenler ile oyun davranışları arasında anlamlı bir farklılık bulunmamıştır. Ancak, çocukların gelişimsel yetersizlik grubuna bağlı olarak annelerin oyun becerileri arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir fark tespit edilmiştir. Çalışmanın sonuçları, farklı gelişimsel özelliklere sahip çocukların anne-çocuk etkileşimlerinde çeşitlilik olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Bu bulgular, özel eğitim uzmanları ve ebeveynler için çocukların özel ihtiyaçlarına daha etkili şekilde yanıt verebilme konusunda farkındalık sağlayabilir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Otizm Spektrum Bozukluğu, Down Sendromu, Tipik Gelişim, Ebeveyn, Oyun Davranışı.

1.Introduction

In addition to being a fundamental stage in an individual's life, the early childhood period is a period in which the rate of development is high, and the learning capacity is at the highest level (Oktay, 2005; Yıldırım & Durmuşoğlu, 2009). This critical period fundamentally affects the individual's future academic, social, and emotional development. Nelson et al. (2009) emphasized how critical the first five years of life are for brain development. They stated that children who grow up in a social environment and enrich their experiences with various stimuli make healthy social, cognitive, and psychological progress. In this context, play in early childhood has a central role in children's development. Play is a natural learning tool that supports children's mental, emotional, social, and physical skills (Bodrova & Leong, 2015). When the literature was analyzed, definitions of play were made. Vygotsky (1967) considered play a process in which children use their imagination, assume specific roles, and participate by following the rules. Hughes (2010) stated that play is as fundamental as sleeping and eating for children's healthy development and education. Canning (2007) defines play as an activity in which children try to discover and understand the external world full of unknowns. In this framework, play enables children to learn about the events, situations, and people around them, and it helps them understand cause-effect relationships (Pehlivan, 2014).

The play-based learning approach is accepted as one of the most effective learning methods in early childhood in Turkey and the world (Kaytez & Durualp, 2014; Pellegrini, 1980; Stagnitti ve diğ., 2017; Wu, 2012). Children can gain awareness, develop various skills, and acquire the right attitudes through play. Play-based learning environments contribute to learning concepts more effectively by facilitating children's mental representations (Şahin, 2015). In this direction, the experiences gained in early childhood significantly impact the individual's future life (Durualp & Aral, 2011).

For children with special needs, peer play is an enjoyable and instructive experience like their typically developing peers (Redepenning & Mundly, 2013). However, the play behaviors of these children usually involve less interaction and may exhibit unusual patterns (Berckelaer-Onnes, 1994; Frost ve diğ., 2008; Tobias, 1994). Children with special needs may acquire play stages later than their typically developing peers. This may be due to limited play opportunities, lack of support, or lack of an appropriate play environment

(Aksoy & Çiftçi, 2020). Although play is an essential learning tool for all children, this process may involve different dynamics for children with special needs. Accordingly, families prioritize finding appropriate environments to meet their children's educational needs (Grygas ve diğ., 2013). In children with special needs development, various interventions are carried out in natural living spaces such as home and school with expert personnel and families (Pletcher & Younggren, 2011). Various interventions are implemented in natural settings such as home and school to support the development of children with special needs. These include family-centered practices where parents are actively involved in supporting their child's growth (Pletcher & Younggren, 2011), naturalistic interventions that integrate learning into everyday routines and environments (Dunst, Trivette, & Hamby, 2010), and play-based approaches that enhance communication and social skills through structured play (Lifter, Mason, & Barton, 2011). Additionally, individualized education programs (IEPs) provide tailored goals and instructional strategies within school settings (Turnbull et al., 2011), while routine-based interventions embed learning opportunities into daily activities, increasing functional use and generalization of skills (McWilliam, 2010). These methods ensure that learning is meaningful, contextually relevant, and developmentally appropriate. These interventions must be supported by teaching techniques that will make learning processes functional and efficient (Tuğrul, 2014).

Mother-child interaction, essential for play, is a fundamental element for the child's lifelong development. The effects of the mother figure on the child's individual characteristics, academic performance, and behaviors are evident (Akgün & Yeşilyaprak, 2011). Positive mother-child interaction and

stimuli provided at an early age make significant contributions to the child's healthy development (Hortaçsu, 2003; Kağıtçıbaşı, 1999). Mother-child plays are a strong bonding tool regarding physical contact and emotional content (Driscoll & Easterbrooks, 2007; Winnicott, 1998).

In this study, the play skills of mothers of typically developing children, children with Down syndrome, and children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) were investigated comparatively. In addition, the differences between mothers' education level, number of children, employment status and age, and play skills were investigated. This study aims to provide essential findings to understand the play skills of mothers of children with different developmental characteristics and to support mother-child interactions.

2. Method

This study aimed to investigate the playing skills of three different groups in a comparative manner. In this direction, a study group of children between the ages of 36-48 months with different developmental characteristics and their mothers was formed. This study is a causal comparison study. Causal-comparative research, also known as ex post facto research, is a non-experimental design used to investigate possible cause-and-effect relationships between variables. Unlike experimental designs, this method does not involve manipulation of the independent variable. Instead, it examines existing differences among groups and attempts to determine the cause of these differences retrospectively (Gall ve diğ., 2007).

2.1. Participants and procedure

This study aimed to investigate the playing skills of three different groups in a comparative manner. In this direction, a study group of children between the ages of 36-48 months with different developmental characteristics and their mothers was formed. The study group included children with Down Syndrome, children affected by ASD (Autism Spectrum Disorder), and children with typical development. The research was conducted with the mothers of children between 36 and 48 months who receive education in rehabilitation centers and preschool education institutions. This group consists of 6 mothers of girls and four mothers of boys with typical development, three mothers of girls, seven mothers of boys with Down Syndrome, and 10 mothers of boys affected by ASD. A total of 30 mothers were included in the study.

The children of the mothers participating in the study should only be in the developmental period of 36-48 months, and the mothers of children outside this age range, children younger than 36 months or older than 48 months, and children diagnosed with an additional disability were excluded from the study. Mothers of children who met these inclusion criteria were included in the study. Demographic information of the mothers who participated in the study is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Findings related to the demographic characteristics of the participants

Demographic Features	n	Percent (%)
Age	24-29	16,7
	30-39	66,6
	40-45	16,7
	Total	100,0
Edu Sta.	Pri. School	13,3
	Middle School	10,0
	High School	20,0
	Associate Degree	6,7
	License	46,7
	Master's Degree	3,3
	Total	100,0

Profession	Housewife	19	63,4
	Teacher	10	33,3
	Nurse	1	3,3
	Total	30	100,0
Number of Children	1	8	26,7
	2	12	40,0
	3	5	16,7
	4	2	6,7
	5	2	6,7
	6	1	3,2
	Total	30	100,0

*Edu Sta=Education Status; Pri. School=Primary School

When the age distribution of the 30 mothers who participated in the study is analyzed, it is seen that the majority of the participants (66.6%; $n=20$) are in the 30-39 age range. The 25-29 and 40-45 age groups are represented by 16.7% ($n=5$) each.

In terms of education level, the most common group of mothers bachelor's degree graduates (46.7%; $n=14$), followed by high school graduates (20%; $n=6$), primary school graduates (13.3%; $n=4$), secondary school graduates (10%; $n=3$) and master's degree graduates (3.3%; $n=1$).

In the occupational distribution, 63.3% ($n=19$) of the mothers were homemakers, while 33.3% ($n=10$) worked as teachers. Finally, when the distribution of mothers according to the number of children they have is analyzed, 12 out of 30 mothers have two children and constitute 40.0% of the group. Mothers with 1 child constitute 26.7% of the group, mothers with 3 children constitute 16.7%, mothers with 6 children constitute 3.2%, and mothers with 4 and 5 children constitute 6.7%.

2.3. Measures

Playing Skills Support Programme Checklist (OBEDEP-KL)

The OBEDEP-CL, developed by Aygürt (2021) to evaluate the play skills of mothers of children with special needs, is a scale consisting of 23 items and based on 3-point Likert-type ("rarely," "sometimes," "always") response options. This checklist systematically analyses mothers' behavioral and pedagogical strategies in their interactions with their children. The literature on play skills and parental interaction was extensively reviewed in developing the scale. Then, the draft items were revised with the feedback of field experts to ensure content validity. A minimum score of 23 and a maximum score of 69 quantitatively reflect mothers' performance levels during play. This scoring range measures the mother's competence in critical areas such as encouraging the child's social participation, supporting language and communication development, developing imitation skills through modeling, and increasing the variety of play. The scale, which was designed to guide mothers of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) to adopt interaction methods appropriate to the individual needs of their children, provides a practical assessment tool for mothers based on the principles of social communication and play-based intervention emphasized by Prizant et al. (2000).

Play Materials and Interaction Process

The study used toys that cover functional, relational, and symbolic play stages to evaluate parent-child interaction. In selecting toys, the objectives of compatibility with children's developmental levels, balancing gender-based preferences, and increasing the intensity of interaction were considered. The materials identified after the pilot studies were categorized into four main categories:

1. **Animal Figures:** Realistically detailed animal figures such as cows, sheep, lions, elephants, and tigers were selected to encourage symbolic play skills (e.g., role-playing or story-making).

2. Fruit/Vegetable Models: Both part-whole (e.g., corn with its stalk) and one-piece (e.g., grape cluster) models such as corn, aubergine, strawberry, banana, and grape were used to observe object use and conceptual association skills during functional play.
3. Interaction-based Toys: Materials such as colored balls and foam bubble sets supported activities that required verbal/non-verbal communication and joint attention between parent and child.
4. Relational Toys: Shape-matching cubes and colored rings are preferred for structured play that develops problem-solving and hand-eye coordination.

It aimed to control external variables by ensuring all participants interacted with the same toy set. Before the video recording started, the mothers were given a standard instruction: "*You can play with any toy you want, in any way you want.*" the researcher left the environment and allowed the natural interaction to be observed. The instructions were not changed throughout the process. Neutral colors and universal themes were preferred to minimize gender orientation in toy selection. The materials were optimized for the cognitive and motor skills of 36- to 48-month-old children. A familiar playground was used instead of a laboratory environment to capture natural interaction. In the present study, a familiar playground environment was deliberately selected instead of a controlled laboratory setting in order to observe mother-child interactions in a natural and ecologically valid context. Since young children are more likely to express themselves freely and engage in authentic social behaviors within environments they recognize and feel comfortable in, the use of a known playground enhances the likelihood of capturing spontaneous and meaningful interaction patterns. Moreover, familiar settings help reduce performance anxiety and increase the quality of caregiver-child communication, which is critical when assessing real-life social and emotional exchanges.

2.4. Data analysis

For the implementation of the study, ethics committee approval and official permissions were obtained from the rehabilitation centers and preschool education institutions affiliated with the Ministry of National Education. After the permission process was completed, face-to-face interviews were conducted in the target institutions (rehabilitation centers and kindergartens in the central districts), and the purpose of the study and participation criteria were shared. The mothers of the children receiving education in the institutions were asked to fill out a family information form covering the children's demographic information and developmental profiles. The collected forms were analyzed, and mothers whose children were between 36 and 48 months of age and did not have additional diagnoses (psychiatric/neurological) were identified. Individual interviews were conducted with these mothers by planning appropriate dates and times. This study aims to compare the play skills of mothers with children aged 36-48 months with Down Syndrome, Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), and typical development. It is a causal-comparative study. Data obtained in the study were analyzed using the IBM SPSS 22 program. To determine whether the data followed a normal distribution so the Shapiro-Wilk test was used due to the small sample size. The results of the normality test showed that the data did not follow a normal distribution, as the significance value was found to be less than 0.05 ($p < 0.04$) at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, non-parametric tests were used for data analysis. The Kruskal-Wallis Test was employed to compare the play skills of mothers with children having Down Syndrome, ASD, and typical development based on their educational status, number of children, and age. Additionally, Kruskal-Wallis was used to compare the play skills of the mothers in the three diagnostic groups.

Pilot Study

To ensure the validity of the data collection protocol, 3 separate pilot studies were conducted before the main study. The pilot participants were a 38-month-old typically developing girl and her mother, a 40-month-old boy with Down Syndrome and his mother, and a 46-month-old boy with ASD and his mother. In these studies, the appropriateness of the video recording time (16 minutes), the compatibility of the toys with the developmental level (capacity to meet functional, relational, and symbolic play needs), and the clarity of the instructions ("You can play with any toy you want") were tested. The pilot findings showed that some materials (e.g., fruit models with poor part-whole relationships) may shorten children's attention span. Accordingly, the materials were revised and used in the main study. In addition, the process of the researcher leaving the environment was standardized in order not to prevent the natural interaction of the mothers.

2.5. Inter-Coder Reliability

During the data collection process, the video recordings were made in a structured environment with the excluded so that the researcher's presence would not affect the participant's behaviors. To ensure coding reliability, all recordings were first analyzed by the primary coder (the researcher). Then, 25% of the randomly selected recordings (8 videos) were re-evaluated by two independent coders with doctoral degrees. The coders rated the mothers' play behaviors according to the OBEDEP-KL criteria, and the level of agreement was calculated using the formula of $Agreement / (Agreement + Disagreement) \times 100$ as suggested by Kırcaali-Iftar and Tekin (1997). As a result, the inter-coder reliability was determined to be 98.4%, and this high level of agreement supported the consistency of the data analysis.

3. Findings

This study aimed to comparatively examine the play skills of mothers of 36-48-month-old children with Down Syndrome (DS), Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), and typically developing children. No statistically significant difference was found in the analyses conducted to determine the effect of the mother's educational status on OBEDEP-KL scores (Table 2). For example, no significant difference was observed between the play behaviors of mothers with a bachelor's degree and mothers with a high school degree ($p>0.05$).

Table 2.

Findings related to mothers' playing skills and educational status

Education	Status	n	Ranking	X2	df	Average	p
Primary School		4	11,50				
Middle School		3	4,83				
High School		6	17,33		9,529	5	0,090
Associate Degree		2	7,75				
License		14	19,18				
Master's Degree		1	16,50				

The findings show no statistically significant difference in mothers' playing skills according to their educational status ($X^2=9,529$; $p=0,090>0,05$). Another sub-objective question of the study was to examine the relationship between the number of children mothers had and their playing skills. In this context, it was analyzed whether the OBEDEP-KL scores showed statistically significant differences according to the number of children, and the results are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3.*Findings related to the number of children the mothers have and their playing skills*

Mothers Number of Children	n	Ranking Average	X ²	df	P
1	8	14,69			
2	12	19,00			
3	5	7,10			
4	2	15,25	8,826	5	0,116
5	2	23,00			
6	1	7,50			

The findings obtained from the analyses show no statistically significant difference between the number of children mothers have and their play skills ($X^2=8,826$; $p=0,116>0,05$). For example, There was no significant difference between mothers with 2 children ($n=12$) and mothers with 1 child ($n=8$) in OBEDEP-KL scores. The scores of mothers with 3 or more children ($n=5$) were similar to the other groups.

It was investigated whether the mothers' scores from the program checklist to support their playing skills differed statistically according to their employment status. Table 4 shows whether there is a statistically significant difference between the working status of the mothers and their playing skills. The results applied to find the answer to this question are given in Table 4.

Table 4.*Findings related to mothers' employment status and playing skills*

Mothers Study Status	N	Average	X ²	df	P
Homemaker	19	13,26			
Teacher	10	20,55	5,361	2	0,069
Nurse	1	7,5			

No statistically significant difference was found in the analyses conducted to determine whether the mothers' employment status (working/non-working) significantly affected their play skills (Table 4). For example, no significant difference was observed between the OBEDEP-KL scores of working mothers ($n=10$; *teacher*) and non-working mothers ($n=19$; *housewife*) ($p>0,05$).

It was examined whether the mothers' scores from the program checklist to support their playing skills differed statistically according to their ages. Table 5 shows whether there is a statistically significant difference between the ages of the mothers and their play playing skills.

Table 5.*Findings related to the age of the mothers and their playing skills*

Mother Age	N	Average	X ²	df	P
24-29	5	17,90			
30-39	20	14,33	1,073	2	0,585
40-45	5	17,80			

The findings obtained as a result of the analysis show that there is no statistically significant difference between the ages of the mothers and their playing skills ($X^2=1,073$; $p=0,585>0,05$). In the analyses conducted to determine whether the age of the mothers had a significant effect on their play skills, no statistically

significant difference was found (Table 5). For example, no significant difference was observed between the OBEDEP-KL scores of mothers in the 30-39 age group ($n=20$) and those of mothers in the 25-29 or 40-45 age groups ($n=5$ each) ($p>0.05$).

It was examined whether there was a statistically significant difference between the play skills of the mothers participating in the study and the disability group of the child. Table 6 shows whether there is a statistically significant difference between the play skills of the mothers and the disability group of the children.

Table 6.

Findings related to mothers' playing skills and children's disability group.

Disability Group	N	Ranking Average	Kruskal-W	df	p
Down Syndrome	10	14,00	21,644	2	0,00
Autism Spectrum	10	7,20			
Typical Development	10	25,30			

In the study, the Kruskal-Wallis H Test was applied to determine whether the differences between the play skills of mothers of children with Down Syndrome (DS), Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), and typically developing children were statistically significant. The results of the analysis showed that there was a statistically significant difference between the groups.

Table 7.

Findings related to mothers' playing skills and children's developmental status

	Standard Error	Test Statistics	p
Autism-Down	3,930	1,730	0,251
Autism-Typical	3,930	-4,605	0,000
Down-Typical	3,930	-2,875	0,012

According to Table 7, it is seen that the statistically significant difference between the mothers' playing skills and the disability group of the children is between ASD-Typical ($P=0.000$) and Down-Typical ($P=0.012$).

4. Discussion

In this study, the fact that there was no significant relationship between mothers' educational level and play skills contradicts the findings of the study conducted by Memiş and Gürsoy (2022), which found significant differences between educational level and "encouraging" and "teaching" skills. The main reason for this difference may be that the groups focussed on and the skills measured in the two studies differ. Memiş and Gürsoy (2022) examined only mothers of typically developing 18-36-month-old children and emphasized the effect of educational level on teaching behaviours. The higher scores of university graduate mothers in encouragement and teaching skills towards their children can be explained by the contribution of formal education to pedagogical knowledge. The research incorporated a heterogeneous sample of mothers, including those with children diagnosed with ASD, Down syndrome, and typically developing children. The complex needs of children with special needs may shape mothers' play behaviours independent of their

level of education. In addition, the focus of the OBEDEP-KL scale on instinctive skills such as social participation, symbolic play, and responsive interaction offers a different measurement area from academic skills associated with education. In addition, the difference in the age range of children (18-36 months vs. 36-48 months) may also be an essential factor. While instructive behaviors are more prominent in early childhood, social interaction skills may come to the fore in preschool. Finally, the fact that the samples of both studies were selected from different sociocultural contexts (for example, all of the mothers in this study had children attending rehabilitation centers) can be considered as another factor that increases the difference between the findings. In this context, it can be concluded that the effect of education level may vary according to the child's diagnostic group, developmental period, and the type of skill measured. This finding suggests that the formal education level of mothers do not directly affect the quality of play-based interactions they establish with their children. It can be suggested that the practical experiences mothers develop for their children's special needs may shape the quality of interaction independent of formal education. Since other variables related to education level (social support, economic resources) were not controlled, the relationship may have remained hidden. In addition, the fact that OBEDEP-KL focuses on behavioral strategies (e.g., sensitivity, non-verbal communication) that are not directly related to education may explain this result.

In this study, the absence of a significant relationship between mothers' educational levels and their play skills aligns with findings from previous research. For instance, Kars (2017) reported no statistically significant differences between education levels and various maternal behaviors, including sensitivity, encouragement, and teaching, among mothers of children diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and developmental delays in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC). Similarly, a study by Sharabi and Marom-Golan (2018) found that higher education levels positively predicted parental involvement, but this effect was significant only among fathers of children with ASD, not mothers. These findings suggest that factors other than formal education, such as practical experience and specialized knowledge related to the child's needs, may play a more crucial role in shaping parental play behaviors, especially in the context of children with developmental challenges. This suggests that the play behaviours of mothers of children with special needs are shaped more by practical experiences and special education skills for the child's complex needs. On the other hand, Işıkoğlu and İrvendi (2008), in a study with parents of typically developing children, found that there were significant differences between educational level and academic play, socio-dramatic play, and encouraging play behaviours. The differences between the child's developmental profile and the nature of the parental role can explain these contradictory results. While parents of typically developing children usually adopt a "friend" role in the play process, parents of children with special needs take on more of a "guide" or "constructivist" role (Dirks & Hadders-Algra, 2011). For example, to support the social communication skills of a child with ASD, the mother may need to develop strategies specific to the individual needs of the child, regardless of the level of education. Research indicates that factors such as practical experience, understanding of the child's specific needs, and emotional adjustment play a more significant role in shaping the behaviors of parents of children with special needs than formal education levels. For instance, a study by Khosravi et al. (2023) found that resilience training reduced parental stress and increased hope and psychological resilience in mothers of children with disabilities. Similarly, research by Guillamón et al. (2013) highlighted that self-efficacy and coping strategies significantly influenced the quality of life and mental health among parents of children with cerebral palsy. These findings underscore the importance of practical training and interventions aimed at enhancing psychological resilience, rather than solely relying on educational support programs, to improve the well-being of parents caring for children with special needs.

This study by Oğuz and Sönmez (2018) revealed that there was no significant relationship between the education level of mothers of children with special needs (36-72 months old diagnosed with ASD) and their interaction behaviours with their children. The fact that there was no difference in the sensitive responsiveness, emotional expressiveness, and achievement-oriented directiveness sub-dimensions of the mothers according to the level of education is consistent with the findings of this study and Kars (2017). This supports that factors such as practical experience, diagnosis-specific strategies, and emotional adjustment

are more determinant than formal education in parents of children with special needs. On the other hand, the finding of significant relationships between education level and interaction quality in studies conducted with parents of typically developing children (Işıkoğlu & İrvendi, 2008) reflects the differences between the developmental profile of the child and the nature of the parental role. While in typical development, parents focus on "playmates" supporting the child's natural learning process, parents of children with special needs adopt a structured and goal-oriented approach to overcome difficulties in the child's communication, social skills, or motor development. Since this approach requires knowledge and expert support specific to the child's needs rather than formal education, the effect of educational level may be secondary.

In this study, the fact that there was no statistically significant difference between the number of children mothers had and their play skills ($\chi^2=8,826$; $p=0,116$) reveals a unique profile regarding the family dynamics of children with special needs. However, studies on typically developing children partially support and contradict this finding. For example, Ekici et al. (2022) and Işıkoğlu and İrvendi (2008) found significant relationships between the number of children and play behaviours in children with typical development, especially in the academic play dimension. The main reason for this difference may be that while parents focus on "playmates" in typical development, parents of children with special needs adopt the "guide" role, and the interactions are structured according to the child's individual needs. Aşık-Öztürk et al. (2018) stated that the participation of children with special needs in group games increased as the number of siblings increased. Still, this situation reflects the child's social adaptation rather than the mother's play skills. The limited social interaction opportunities of children with special needs may cause siblings to assume a critical role. In this study, the fact that mothers' play skills were independent of the number of children may be explained by factors such as intra-family role distribution, expert support, and diagnosis-specific needs of the child. In conclusion, interaction strategies of mothers of children with special needs are shaped by practical experience and the child's individual needs rather than demographic factors such as formal education or the number of children. These findings emphasize that family support programs should focus on the child's needs and the family's resources rather than the number of children.

The fact that there was no statistically significant difference between mothers' employment status and play skills ($\chi^2=5,361$; $p=0,069$) shows that the interaction strategies of mothers of children with special needs are shaped independently of working conditions. This finding is consistent with the study conducted by Kök and Ünal (2018) with the mothers of typically developing children, in which no significant difference was found between working status and the parent-child relationship. Similarly, Kars (2017) found that there was no significant relationship between employment status and interaction quality of mothers of children diagnosed with ASD and developmental delay. This suggests that mothers of both typical and children with special needs can maintain their ability to spend quality time with their children regardless of their employment status. However, although some studies suggest that working mothers may decrease their interaction time due to time constraints, contrary to these studies, it is seen that mothers can close this gap by having more focused and intensive interactions with their children during non-working hours. Especially for mothers of children with special needs, developing structured play strategies for the child's needs may enable them to maintain their skills independently of their working status. In addition, factors such as the occupational diversity of working mothers (e.g., jobs requiring pedagogical experience such as teaching) and flexible working hours may explain this result. In conclusion, the limited effect of mothers' employment status on play skills suggests that factors such as sensitivity to child needs, time management, and social support mechanisms are more determinant. These findings emphasize the importance of flexible parenting models and child-centered interventions instead of working status in family support policies.

The fact that there was no statistically significant difference between mothers' age and play skills ($\chi^2=1,073$; $p=0,585$) shows that mothers' interactional behaviors are shaped independently of age. This finding is consistent with studies involving mothers of typically developing children and children with special needs. For example, Memiş and Gürsoy (2022), in a study conducted with mothers of typically developing children aged 18-36 months, found that age had no significant effect on the sub-dimensions of

the PICCOLO scale. Similarly, Kök and Ünal (2018) found no significant relationship between the age of mothers of typically developing preschool children and their relationships with their children. These results suggest that mothers' play skills are determined by dynamics such as individual characteristics, emotional bonding, and sensitivity to the needs of the child rather than age. This may be even more evident in mothers of children with special needs, as their interaction strategies are directly related to their ability to adapt to the child's diagnostic needs and learning styles. The limited effect of age indicates that mothers' experiential learning and child-centred adaptation abilities come to the fore. Moreover, the fact that the measurement tools focus on skills such as sensitivity, reactivity, and communication, which are unrelated to age, supports this conclusion.

The study revealed the differences between the play behaviors of mothers of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and Down Syndrome (DS) and mothers of typically developing children. The findings support that the interaction strategies of mothers of children with ASD and DS are shaped according to the developmental needs of their children, and this is consistent with the literature. In line with the studies of Özenmiş Ünsal (2003) and Şahin (2022), who stated that mothers of children with Down Syndrome had difficulty in directing their children's attention to toys and focused more on social interaction, it was observed that mothers in the DS group assumed a more directive and guiding role. This suggests that the cognitive and linguistic delays of children with DS require mothers to provide structured support during play actively. Mothers of children with ASD, on the other hand, exhibited more passive and limited responsiveness compared to the typically developing group. In studies conducted by Doğan et al. (2016) and Kars and Akı (2020), it was stated that the deficiencies in the functional play skills and repetitive behaviors of children with ASD affected the interaction style of mothers. For example, children with ASD showing indifference to toys or exhibiting obsessive behaviors may cause mothers to focus more on behavior management. Ceyhun et al. (2016) emphasized that mothers of children with typical development were more responsive and supportive during play. This finding suggests that while mothers of typically developing children naturally encourage the child's exploratory behaviors, mothers of children with ASD and DS adopt a more intrusive approach to overcome the child's limitations.

4.1. Conclusion

This study comparatively analyzed the play skills of mothers of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), Down Syndrome (DS), and typically developing children and revealed the dynamics specific to the diagnostic groups. The findings showed that demographic factors such as age, education level, employment status, or number of children did not significantly affect mothers' play skills. Still, the child's diagnostic group played a determining role in shaping the mother's interaction strategies. In particular, mothers of children with ASD and DS adopted a more structured, directive approach that focused on the child's individual needs compared to those of the typically developing group. While mothers of children with ASD exhibited more passive and behavior management-oriented interactions due to their children's limited interests and repetitive behaviors, mothers of children with DS adopted a more active and guiding role to increase social interaction. These findings emphasize that mothers of children with special needs develop adaptive strategies shaped by practical experiences and expert support specific to the child's diagnosis, whereas formal education or demographic characteristics appear secondary in this process.

However, the study has several limitations. It was limited to children aged 36–48 months diagnosed with ASD, DS, and typical development, along with their mothers. Although efforts were made to create a familiar setting, data were collected in a structured environment, which may have initially required participants to adapt to the physical setting. Moreover, the awareness of being recorded might have influenced mothers' behavior during play, potentially limiting the authenticity of observed interactions. In future studies, the relationship between mothers' emotional adjustment processes and play skills can be examined with qualitative methods. In addition, universal intervention models can be created by making intercultural comparisons in different diagnostic groups. Future research may focus on longitudinal designs and culturally diverse populations to further explore maternal adaptation strategies in play interactions.

5. Statement of Researchers

Footnote: This article is based on the data of the 1st author's master's thesis.

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No funding was received for the conduct of this study.

Ethical approval and informed consent statements

This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved (E-97105791-050.01.01-2755). Informed parental consent was obtained from all participants. Informed consent for participation has been obtained in writing.

Data Availability Statement

The data are available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author due to privacy restrictions

Any other identifying information related to the authors and/or their institutions, funders, approval committees, etc, that might compromise anonymity.

The authors declare that there is no information that needs to be stated under this heading.

Community involvement statement

From the beginning of the research, the authors took an active role in every stage of the process, including the selection of research methods, the design of the study, the analysis and interpretation of the findings, as well as the evaluation of the draft manuscript. Following the pilot study, discussions were held on the appropriateness of the materials, clarity and accessibility of the instructions and a common conclusion was reached.

References

- Akgün, S., & Yeşilyaprak, B. (2011). Anne-çocuk etkileşiminin çocuğun gelişimi üzerindeki etkileri. *Çocuk ve Ergen Ruh Sağlığı Dergisi*, 18(2), 71-79.
- Aksoy, S., & Çiftçi, R. (2020). Özel gereksinimli çocukların oyun davranışları. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 45(200), 193-209.
- Aşık-Öztürk, M., Ahmetoğlu, E., & Acar, İ. H. (2018). Normal gelişim gösteren ve özel eğitim ihtiyacı olan çocukların grup ortamlarındaki oyun davranışlarının incelenmesi. VIII. *International Balkan and Near Eastern Social Sciences Congress Series*, Plovdiv/Bulgaria, 506-512
- Aygürt, S. (2021). Özel gereksinimli çocukların annelerinin oyun becerilerinin değerlendirilmesi: OBEDEP-KL ölçeği [Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi]. Hasan Kalyoncu Üniversitesi.
- Berckelaer-Onnes, I. A. (1994). Play in children with developmental disabilities: A review. *Early Child Development and Care*, 98(1), 85-99.
- Bodrova, E., & Leong, D. J. (2015). *Tools of the mind: The Vygotskian approach to early childhood education* (2nd ed.). Pearson.
- Canning, N. (2007). Play as a tool for learning: A review. *Educational Psychology*, 27(5), 633-647.

- Ceyhun, İ., Çelik, F., & Aksoy, M. (2016). Tipik gelişim gösteren çocuk annelerinin oyun becerilerinin değerlendirilmesi. *Çocuk Gelişimi Dergisi*, 10(2), 95-105. Doi: 10.18039/ajesi.737698
- Dirks, T., & Hadders-Algra, M. (2011). The role of the family in intervention of infants at high risk of cerebral palsy: A systematic review. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, 53(Suppl. 4), 62-67. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8749.2011.04067.x>
- Doğan, S., Kaya, G., & Yılmaz, S. (2016). Otizm spektrum bozukluğu tanılı çocukların annelerinin oyun becerilerinin incelenmesi. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 43(5), 87-96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-016-2835-x>
- Driscoll, K. R., & Easterbrooks, M. A. (2007). Parenting and child development: Early parent-child interaction. *Journal of Developmental and Behavioral Pediatrics*, 28(3), 203-214.
- Dunst, C. J., Trivette, C. M., & Hamby, D. W. (2010). Meta-analysis of the effectiveness of naturalistic interventions for increasing expressive language production. *Topics in Early Childhood Special Education*, 30(3), 135-146. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0271121410376411>
- Durualp, E., & Aral, N. (2011). Erken çocukluk dönemi ve eğitimde oyun tabanlı öğrenme. *Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 6(2), 24-33.
- Frost, J. L., Wortham, S. C., & Reifel, S. (2008). *Play and child development*. Pearson Education.
- Gall, M. D., Gall, J. P., & Borg, W. R. (2007). *Educational research: An introduction* (8th ed.). Pearson Education
- Grygas, A., Campbell, P., & Abery, B. (2013). Family needs in early childhood intervention for children with disabilities. *Journal of Early Intervention*, 35(4), 318-334. doi: [10.1097/00005721-200507000-00011](https://doi.org/10.1097/00005721-200507000-00011)
- Guillamón, N., Nieto, R., Pousada, M., Redolar, D., Muñoz, E., Hernández, E., Boixadós, M., & Gómez-Zúñiga, B. (2013). Quality of life and mental health among parents of children with cerebral palsy: The influence of self-efficacy and coping strategies. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 22(11-12), 1579-1590. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.12124>
- Hortaçsu, N. (2003). Anne-çocuk etkileşiminin çocuğun gelişimine etkisi. *Türk Psikoloji Dergisi*, 18(1), 26-42.
- Hughes, C. (2010). The importance of play in child development. *Journal of Early Childhood Education*, 5(1), 31-43.
- Işıkoğlu, S., & İrvendi, S. (2008). Tipik gelişim gösteren çocukların ebeveynlerinin oyun becerilerinin değerlendirilmesi. *Çocuk Gelişimi ve Eğitim Dergisi*, 5(1), 28-36.
- Kağıtçıbaşı, C. (1999). *Yeni insan: Çocuk gelişimi ve psikolojisi*. Varlık Yayınları.
- Kars, M. (2017). Özel gereksinimli çocukların annelerinin oyun becerileri: Kıyaslamalı bir inceleme. *Gelişimsel Psikoloji Dergisi*, 12(3), 55-70.
- Kars, M., & Aki, E. (2020). Otizm spektrum bozukluğu tanılı çocuk annelerinin oyun becerileri: Bir inceleme. *Gelişimsel Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 8(1), 52-65.
- Kaytez, N., Kaytez, N., & Durualp, E. (2014). Türkiye'de okul öncesinde oyun ile ilgili yapılan lisansüstü tezlerin incelenmesi. *International Journal of Turkish Education Sciences*, 2014(2), 110-122.
- Khosravi, Z., Sadeghi, R., & Faramarzi, M. (2023). Effect of resilience training on stress, hope, and psychological toughness of mothers living with mentally and physically disabled children. *BMC Pediatrics*, 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-024-04828-6>
- Kırcaali-İftar, M., & Tekin, S. (1997). Görüş birliği ve güvenilirlik hesaplamaları: Bir ölçüm değerlendirme yöntemi. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 22(103), 50-58.
- Kök, İ., & Ünal, E. (2018). Çalışan annelerin çocuklarıyla etkileşimleri: Eğitim düzeyi ve meslek türü üzerine bir inceleme. *Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 9(4), 100-112.
- Lifter, K., Mason, E. J., & Barton, E. E. (2011). Children's play: The roots of reading. *zero to three*, 31(4), 28-35.
- McWilliam, R. A. (2010). *Working with families of young children with special needs*. Guilford Press.
- Memiş, M., & Gürsoy, D. (2022). Eğitim düzeyi ile oyun becerileri arasındaki ilişki: Bir araştırma. *Psiko-Eğitim Dergisi*, 13(2), 45-57.
- Nelson, C. A., Fox, N. A., & Zeanah, C. H. (2009). The importance of early experience in human development. *American Psychologist*, 64(3), 173-181.
- Oğuz, E., & Sönmez, M. (2018). Özel gereksinimli çocukların annelerinin etkileşim stratejileri. *Çocuk Gelişimi ve Rehabilitasyon Dergisi*, 4(3), 98-108.
- Oktay, A. (2005). *Erken çocukluk dönemi gelişimi*. Eğitim Yayınevi.
- Özenmiş Ünsal, B. (2003). Down sendromlu çocukların annelerinin oyun becerileri. *Psikolojik Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 5(1), 32-45.
- Pehlivan, B. (2014). Oyun ve çocuk gelişimi: Temel kavramlar ve teoriler. *Gelişim Dergisi*, 12(1), 50-64.
- Pellegrini, A. D. (1980). The role of play in cognitive development. *Child Development*, 51(1), 59-67.
- Pletcher, S., & Younggren, N. (2011). Early intervention and family involvement in children with disabilities. *Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 30(2), 85-97.
- Prizant, B. M., Wetherby, A. M., & Rydell, P. (2000). Social communication and play in children with autism. *Early Development and Parenting*, 10(1), 23-33.

- Redepenning, L. L., & Mundly, M. L. (2013). Play and children with disabilities: A review of the literature. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 41(4), 227-235.
- Şahin, B. (2015). Oyun temelli öğrenme ve çocuk gelişimi. *Eğitimde Yenilikçi Yaklaşımlar Dergisi*, 7(1), 34-45.
- Şahin, Z. (2022). Down sendromlu çocukların annelerinin sosyal etkileşim stratejileri. *Çocuk ve Aile Psikolojisi Dergisi*, 11(2), 101-112.
- Stagnitti, K., O'Connor, R., & Sheppard, L. (2017). Play-based interventions and early childhood development. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 49(2), 221-233.
- Tobias, S. (1994). The role of play in children with autism. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 24(1), 43-57.
- Tuğrul, B. (2014). Erken çocukluk dönemi müdahaleleri ve oyun temelli yaklaşımlar. *Eğitim ve Psikolojik Danışmanlık Dergisi*, 15(3), 121-130.
- Turnbull, A., Turnbull, R., Shank, M., & Smith, S. (2011). *Exceptional lives: Special education in today's schools* (6th ed.). Pearson.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1967). Play and its role in the development of the child. *Psychology of Play*, 243-253.
- Westby, C. (2000). Play: A work of meaning-making. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 2(2), 133-150.
- Winnicott, D. W. (1998). *The child and the family*. Penguin Books.
- Wu, L. (2012). Play-based learning strategies in early childhood education. *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, 10(2), 156-169.
- Yaşar Ekici, D., Yılmaz, N., & Özkul, S. (2022). Tipik gelişim gösteren çocuk annelerinin oyun davranışları: Sosyo-demografik faktörler ve oyun türleri. *Çocuk ve Aile Dergisi*, 12(3), 60-72.
- Yıldırım, A., & Durmuşoğlu, M. (2009). *Erken çocukluk dönemi gelişimi ve eğitim*. Eğitim Yayınları.